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Study on Potentially Toxic Benthic Dinoflagellate Assemblages on Dead Corals in Nha Trang Bay, Vietnam

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Abstract

Dead branching coral samples were collected in Nha Trang Bay to isolate benthic dinoflagellates. The identification and taxonomic observation of benthic dinoflagellates were based on cell size, shape, surface morphology, and thecal plate structure using light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy. A total of 27 benthic dinoflagellate species belonging to 5 orders were identified from dead corals. The cell density of dinoflagellates varied spatially. During the dry season, the highest density reached 17.8 cells/cm², while in the rainy season, the highest density was 15.7 cells/cm². Five species of *Gambierdiscus australes*, *G. carpenteri*, *G. caribaeus*, *G. polynesiensis*, *G. belizeanus*, which are known to cause Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP), were also detected, although their cell densities were low, reaching 2.8 cells/cm² in the dry season and 0.5 cells/cm² in the rainy season.

Keywords: Benthic dinoflagellates; Ciguatera; Nha Trang Bay; Vietnam

Introduction

Benthic dinoflagellates, belonging to the phylum Dinophyta, are distributed in tropical and subtropical marine regions. They can be found on sandy bottoms, on the surface of dead corals, seagrasses, macroalgae, debris, and even on some artificial substrates (Faust, 1995; Hoppenrath et al., 2014; Tester et al., 2014). Among them, some species have been identified as the cause of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP), notably those belonging to the genus *Gambierdiscus*. Ciguatoxins (CTXs) and maitotoxins (MTXs) are the two main toxins produced by certain species of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* (Munday et al., 2017; Rhodes et al., 2014). CTXs can accumulate in benthic organisms and subsequently undergo bioaccumulation in certain predatory reef fish through natural food chain (Leite et al., 2021; Holmes and Lewis, 2022). When humans consume fish or shellfish contaminated with CTX toxins, they may suffer from a type of food poisoning known as Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) (Costa et al., 2018; Pisapia et al., 2017; Chateau-Degat et al., 2005).

Although the symptoms of CFP are non-specific, they mainly manifest in the gastrointestinal, muscle, cardiovascular, and nervous systems (Lehane and Lewis, 2000). It is estimated that ciguatera affects 50,000–500,000 people worldwide each year (Soliño and Costa, 2020). Although this illness has existed for centuries, its diagnosis, prevention, treatment, and management remain major challenges (Friedman et al., 2017; L'Herondelle et al., 2020). Today, the global spread of CFP has led to *Gambierdiscus* species and their toxins being considered a worldwide concern for both the environment and human health (Wang et al., 2022). Over the past decade in Vietnam, studies on the taxonomy and ecology of benthic dinoflagellates have mainly focused on species attached to macroalgae, seagrasses, and sandy bottoms (Ho et al., 2010; Ho and Nguyen, 2014; Ho and H'Yon, 2019; 2021; Nguyen et al., 2021; 2023; Ho and Wang, 2023), while benthic dinoflagellates on dead corals have been less studied, and information about them remains limited (Chu, 2002). Recently, a hypothesis has suggested that disturbances to coral reefs create new surfaces, facilitating the growth of algal layers on coral surfaces, and that some benthic dinoflagellate species

(*Gambierdiscus*) may grow on coral surfaces (Holmes and Lewis, 2025). Toxicological studies on the species *G. toxicus* in Vietnam have shown that it produces predominantly the toxin 2,3-dihydroxy P-CTX-3C, followed by P-CTX-3C, and only a very small amount of P-CTX-4A/B (Roeder et al., 2010). Based on research documents, we assessed the species composition of benthic dinoflagellates and the density fluctuations of several dominant species on dead corals in Nha Trang Bay. This study contributes to a better understanding of the distribution of benthic dinoflagellates, with particular attention to *Gambierdiscus* species that have the potential to produce toxins causing Ciguatera Fish Poisoning.

Materials and methods

Dead coral samples were collected at 5 stations during the dry and rainy seasons in Nha Trang Bay (Fig. 1). Using SCUBA diving, branching dead coral samples were gently collected at depths of approximately 2-6 m and placed into 500-1,000 ml plastic bags. Environmental factors such as temperature, salinity, and pH were also measured on-site using portable instruments at the dead coral sampling locations.

Fig. 1. Map showing the sampling location in Nha Trang Bay

In the laboratory, the collected dead coral samples were placed in plastic jars with lids and vigorously shaken several times to detach benthic dinoflagellates from the coral substrate. The dead coral fragments were separated to calculate their surface area, and the water containing the algae was transferred to another plastic jar. The samples were then filtered and rinsed with seawater through a series of sieves with decreasing mesh sizes: 900, 250, 125, 64, 32, and 20 μm , discarding the material retained on the 250 μm and 125 μm sieves.

The material retained on the 64 μm , 32 μm , and 20 μm sieves was examined and observed using a stereomicroscope. The samples were divided into two parts: qualitative sample and quantitative sample. The wild cells were observed either live or preserved in Lugol's iodine solution using a light microscope. The thecal plates of dinoflagellate species were observed after staining with Calcofluor White M2R using a microscope. Images of the algae were captured with a digital camera. For scanning electron microscopy, natural samples were first examined under a light or fluorescence microscope to identify the target cells for scanning. Once a suitable sample was selected, a drop of the sample was placed in the center of a 5 μm pore diameter carbon filter membrane in a filter holder (Millipore). The filter and samples were rinsed several times with distilled water. Ethanol was applied in increasing concentrations: 15, 30, 50, 70, and 90% to dehydrate the samples. Finally, the samples were dried with absolute ethanol (99.99%). The filter membrane containing the samples was then mounted on an aluminum stub pre-coated with a carbon adhesive film of similar diameter to the filter membrane and sputter-coated with gold using a vacuum sputter coater. The samples were observed using a scanning electron microscope.

Branching coral samples, after the algae were removed, were geometrically shaped and their surface area was estimated (cm^2). The number of dinoflagellate cells on the coral surface was determined using a 1 mL Sedgewick-Rafter counting chamber, and the density of dinoflagellate cells was calculated per unit of coral surface area (cells/cm^2).

Results and discussion

Species composition

A total of 27 benthic dinoflagellate species on dead corals in Nha Trang Bay were identified, belonging to five orders. The order Prorocentrales included 6 species, Dinophysiales 2 species, Gonyaulacales 14 species, Gymnodiniales 3 species, and Peridiniales 2 species (Table 1). Some genera were dominant in species number, such as *Prorocentrum* (6 species) and *Gambierdiscus* (5 species). The species *Coolia malayensis*, *C. tropicalis*, *Sinophysis canaliculata*, *S. microcephala*, *Ostreopsis lenticularis*, *O. siamensis*, *Gambierdiscus carpenteri*, *G. caribaeus*, *G. polynesiensis*, *G. belizeanus*, *Bysmatrum granulatum*, *Prorocentrum concavum*, *P. emarginatum*, *P. lima*, and *P. rhathymum* had high occurrence frequencies. Some species, such as *Prorocentrum arenarium*, *P. tropicalis*, *G. australes*, *Fukuyoa yasumotoi*, and *F. ruetzleri*, were very rare.

Compared with previous studies, among the 27 benthic dinoflagellate species found in Nha Trang Bay, five species belong to *Gambierdiscus*, which are capable of producing CTX and MTX toxins (Rhodes et al., 2014; Clausing et al., 2024; Estevez et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2021; Fernández-Herrera et al., 2024). Before 1999, *Gambierdiscus* was considered a monotypic genus. However, over the past decade, 19 species have been described in this genus, including: *G. toxicus*, *G. australes*, *G. balechii*, *G. belizeanus*, *G. caribaeus*, *G. carolinianus*, *G. carpenteri*, *G. cheloniae*, *G. excentricus*, *G. holmesii*, *G. honu*, *G. jejuensis*, *G. lapillus*, *G. lewissi*, *G. pacificus*, *G. polynesiensis*, *G. scabrosus*, *G. silvae*, and *G. vietnamensis* (Nguyen-Ngoc et al., 2023; Murray et al., 2024). To date, four species of the genus *Fukuyoa* have been described: *F. yasumotoi*, *F. ruetzleri*, *F. paulensis*, and *F. koreensis* (Gómez et al., 2015; Li et al., 2020). The species *F. yasumotoi* and *F. ruetzleri* were also found in this study. Previously, *F. ruetzleri* was detected on sandy bottoms (Ho and H'Yon, 2021), and *F. yasumotoi* was also found on macroalgae (Ho and Nguyen, 2009a). Both species are capable of producing MTX toxins (Holmes, 1998; Leung et al., 2018). The species *C. tropicalis* had a high occurrence frequency in this study and is commonly found attached to macroalgae (Ho and Nguyen, 2014). Recent research has shown that *C. tropicalis* produces toxins that are derivatives similar to gambierone, a toxin that can cause Ciguatera Fish Poisoning, similar to some *Gambierdiscus* species (De Azevedo Tibiriçá et al., 2020).

Table 1. List of dinoflagellate species identified and the occurrences at Nha Trang Bay

S. No.	Species	Occurrence
	Order: Prorocentrales	
1	<i>Prorocentrum rhathymum</i>	C
2	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	C
3	<i>Prorocentrum concavum</i>	F
4	<i>Prorocentrum emarginatum</i>	F
5	<i>Prorocentrum arenarium</i>	R
6	<i>Prorocentrum tropicalis</i>	R
	Order: Dinophysiales	
7	<i>Sinophysis canaliculata</i>	F
8	<i>Sinophysis microcephala</i>	F
	Order: Gonyaulacales	
9	<i>Gambierdiscus australes</i>	R
10	<i>Gambierdiscus carpenteri</i>	F
11	<i>Gambierdiscus caribaeus</i>	F
12	<i>Gambierdiscus polynesiensis</i>	F
13	<i>Gambierdiscus belizeanus</i>	F
14	<i>Coolia tropicalis</i>	F
15	<i>Coolia malayensis</i>	F
16	<i>Coolia canariensis</i>	F
17	<i>Coolia aerolata</i>	R
18	<i>Ostreopsis siamensis</i>	C
19	<i>Ostreopsis lenticularis</i>	C
20	<i>Ostreopsis ovata</i>	C
21	<i>Fukuyoa yasumotoi</i>	R
22	<i>Fukuyoa ruetzleri</i>	R
	Order: Peridiniales	
23	<i>Bysmatrum granulatum</i>	F
24	<i>Thecadinium pseudokofoidii</i>	R
	Order: Gymnodiniales	
25	<i>Amphidinium carterae</i>	R
26	<i>Amphidinium operculatum</i>	F
27	<i>Amphidinium herdmanii</i>	R

C- Common, F-Frequent and R-Rare

Cell Density

The results showed that benthic dinoflagellate density varied spatially. During the dry season, the average density was 10.2 cells/cm², with the 2 nearshore stations reaching 17.8 cells/cm², higher than the other 3 stations. In the rainy season, the average density of benthic dinoflagellates was 9.7 cells/cm², with the highest density of 15.7 cells/cm² (station 4), followed by station 5 with a density of 11 cells/cm². The three nearshore stations (stations 1, 2, and 3) had lower densities, ranging from 4.6 to 9.3 cells/cm² (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Density of benthic dinoflagellates during the dry and rainy seasons from 5 stations (St.)

Fig. 3. Cell density of benthic dinoflagellate groups in the dry season (left) and the rainy season (right) from 5 stations (St.) G: *Gambierdiscus*, O: *Ostreopsis*, P: *Prorocentrum*, C: *Coolia*

Most benthic dinoflagellate species thrive at salinities of 28–34‰ and optimal temperatures of 25–29°C (Bomber et al., 1988; Morton et al., 1992). During the two sampling periods, seawater temperature did not vary significantly between the two seasons, ranging from 25–29°C, salinity ranged from 32–33.5‰, and seawater pH varied from 7.8 to 8.2. This is one of the environmental factors favorable for algal growth. During the rainy season, seawater salinity decreases; however, this change is minimal and does not significantly affect algal development. Nevertheless, higher suspended solids in the rainy season and lower seawater transparency reduce light intensity in the areas where benthic dinoflagellates are distributed (stations 1 and 2), which in turn affects their growth and distribution.

In both the dry and rainy seasons, species of the genera *Prorocentrum* and *Ostreopsis* consistently showed dominant densities at the survey stations. During the dry season, the highest density of *Prorocentrum* spp. was recorded at 11.8 cells/cm² (station 3), and the density of *Ostreopsis* reached 9.7 cells/cm² (station 1). In contrast, during the rainy season, *Ostreopsis* dominated all stations, with the highest density reaching 12.6 cells/cm² (station 4), while *Prorocentrum* densities ranged from 1.3–3.9 cells/cm² (Fig. 3).

Five species of the genus *Gambierdiscus* were also detected and typically appeared during the dry season, however, their densities were low, reaching 2.8 cells/cm² in the dry season and 0.5 cells/cm² in the rainy season. Similarly, species of the genus *Coolia* were present at low densities but were generally present at all survey stations. Overall, the average density of benthic dinoflagellates on dead corals, as well as the densities of the harmful species *Coolia* spp. and *Gambierdiscus* spp., in Nha Trang Bay during both survey periods, were low. The densities of species in the genera *Sinophysis*, *Amphidinium*, *Bysmatrum*, *Thecadinium*, and *Fukuyoa* were very low.

Comparing with some studies on benthic dinoflagellates on various macroalgae, the density of *Gambierdiscus* spp. on Gambier Island in May 2008 was recorded at 400,000 cells/g of fresh algae (Chinain et al., 2010); in Belize, 450 cells/g of fresh algae; and on Réunion Island, Indian Ocean, 120

cells/g of fresh algae (Quod and Turquet, 1996). In some marine areas of Vietnam, at Con Dao, algal densities on certain macroalgae were: 3,900 cells/g of fresh *Sargassum*, 3,100 cells/g of fresh *Galaxaura* or *Dictyota*, and 2,700 cells/g of fresh *Padina* (Ho and Nguyen, 2009b). In the Northeast Cay area, in May 2007, the highest algal densities reached 819,275 cells/g of fresh *Padina*, followed by 280,865 cells/g of fresh *Caulerpa*, 256,249 cells/g of the seagrass *Thalassodendron ciliatum*, and 43,044 cells/g of fresh *Halimeda*. Among them, *Coolia monotis* was the dominant species in the dinoflagellate community. The density of this species also varied greatly among different substrates, reaching the highest at 789,304 cells/g of fresh *Padina*, followed by 255,072 cells/g of fresh *Caulerpa*, and 256,249 cells/g of seagrass *Thalassodendron ciliatum* (Ho and Nguyen, 2008).

Conclusion

The results of this study provided data on species composition and density of some benthic dinoflagellate assemblages on dead corals. Species capable of causing Ciguatera Fish Poisoning, belonging to the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*, were confirmed. The density of benthic dinoflagellates on dead corals varied spatially, with no significant difference between the dry and rainy seasons. *Ostreopsis* spp. and *Prorocentrum* spp. were dominant in terms of density, while harmful species belonging to the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* were low. The influence of environmental factors on the growth, distribution and toxicology of species causing Ciguatera Fish Poisoning needs to be investigated further.

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Author Contributions

Ho VT: Supervision, methodology, writing-review, and editing; H'Yon NB: Methodology, data analysis, original draft preparation; Le HP, Phan MT, Phan KH: Investigation, methodology. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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